

Noninvasive Facial Rejuvenation with Dermal Fillers and Neurotoxins, Public's Preference: A Survey Report

Li Guang Shuai^{1*}, Muhammad Tipu Sultan¹, Liu Wen Hui¹

¹Department of Plastic Surgery, First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, No.1 Jinshui road, Henan, China

Accepted May 27,2021

Published May 30,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Li Guang Shuai,

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4865004>

Pages: 257-274

Funding: No funding received

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Guang Shuai, L., Tipu Sultan, M., & Wen Hui, L. (2021). Noninvasive Facial Rejuvenation with Dermal Fillers and Neurotoxins, Public's Preference: A Survey Report. *North American Academic Research*, 4(5), 257-274. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4865004>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Background: At present, mostly plastic surgeons and dermatologists provide minimally invasive cosmetic injection procedure services with dermal fillers and neurotoxins. However, the professional background and technical characteristics of the two are different. The preference of lay public for specialist type in performing dermal filler and neuromodulator procedures for cosmetic purposes is unknown. **Methods:** An online survey was conducted for a period of 2 weeks and surveyees were sampled using purposive sampling method on Instagram. Participants were asked a series of questions to choose their preferred specialist for performing cosmetic injection procedures. Additionally, rate of satisfaction of patients with their respective doctors, incidence of posttreatment complications in patients and their successful or unsuccessful management by their respective specialists were measured. **Results:** Two hundred and one respondents undertook the survey. Plastic Surgeons were identified as the most preferable specialist to perform cosmetic injection procedures (59.4%), plastic surgeons were also deemed to be the most skilled professionals among other specialists for such procedures (60.7%). Patients who already have history of such procedures, mostly went to plastic surgeons (53.6%). Additionally, patients who chose plastic surgeons as their injectors reported a higher degree of satisfaction and successful management of their posttreatment complications as compared to dermatologists and other specialists. **Conclusion:** Plastic surgeons are recognized as the preferred specialist over dermatologists and other specialists to perform injectable procedures. Patients of plastic surgeons express greater degree of satisfaction as compared to patients of other injectors. Post- procedure complications in patients are inevitable, however successful treatment of such complications by the particular injector leads to a more satisfied patient who develops a trust on that particular specialist for future procedures.

Keywords: PLASTIC SURGEONS VS DERMATOLOGISTS, DERMAL FILLERS, NEUROTOXINS, SURVEY, PUBLICS'S PEEFERENCE

Introduction

The exploding popularity of dermal fillers, substantial increase in patient population, and demand for swift and long-lasting results which are appealing for patients, have led to an increase of aesthetic practitioners all over North American Academic Research, 4(5) | May 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4865004> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 257

the world. In addition to aesthetic physicians and surgeons, the number of nondoctor healthcare workers such as nurse practitioners, physician's assistants, medical and dental assistants as well as nonmedical people also started to perform aesthetic procedures with injectables.^{1,2} It's astonishing to see advertisements on social media of various aesthetic clinics with sometimes highly exaggerated claims regarding noninvasive aesthetic treatments targeting the millennials active on social media. Millennials are more likely than any other age group to consider medical therapies such as facial augmentation with fillers and toxins³. From dentists⁴ to orthopedics⁵ and from general practitioners to nurses⁶ and to a surprising degree, even some non-medical persons and quacks⁷ have found to be injecting people with fillers and Botox. There have been even cases of even self-administration of hyaluronic acid filler by some patients leading to severe complications.⁸ Poor injection techniques, insufficient training or no formal training of the injectors, have led to increased incidence of moderate to severe complications associated with such treatments.^{9,10,11}

Among the aesthetic practitioners, the most well-trained specialists in this particular arena are Plastic surgeons and dermatologists. In terms of training both specialists differ a lot but overlap in the field of cosmetic medicine. Over the years both dermatologists and plastic surgeon have been performing noninvasive facial cosmetic procedures typically with dermal fillers and neurotoxins. Compared to the dermatology's and plastic surgery's residency training, other specialty doctors, nondoctors healthcare providers and especially the nonmedical people lack the formal, comprehensive and advanced training in performing medical procedures such as soft tissue augmentation with injectables. As a resultant consequence, such procedures are often performed with little to no oversight in place in many cities of many countries.¹²

There are only few studies that explore the public's views on which experts are best suited and most trained to conduct these minimally invasive aesthetic procedures. According to our findings, previously two studies have been conducted in which the general public was surveyed regarding their preferential healthcare provider for aesthetic treatments. In one study, the general public was surveyed by an online survey. Participants were asked to choose their preferred health care provider for various cosmetic and surgical procedures. Plastic surgeons and dermatologists were chosen as the most favored doctors as 47.3 % participants chose plastic surgeons and 44.6 % chose dermatologists. Plastic surgeons were marginally favored for botulinum toxin injections, accompanied by dermatologists (50.6 % vs 38.4 %).¹³ In another study, a survey was conducted and data of 1015 females, was collected. According to the results, patients who visited plastic surgeons for noninvasive aesthetic procedures, a higher percentage (57%) showed satisfaction with their results and outcomes. Those patients who chose non-plastic aesthetic physicians, only 46 % showed satisfaction with their results and for the patients who visited non-core providers for similar treatments, only 41% showed their satisfaction.¹⁴

It's critical to determine which specialists, medical or nonmedical people, the public and cosmetic patients prefer to perform injectable procedures. The aim of this research is to look at laypeople's and some patients' (with history of having procedures of injectables) opinions and their perceptions of different specialties' expertise in conducting procedures of facial rejuvenation with injectables.

Materials and methods

Questionnaire: An online survey was conducted by using google survey (<https://docs.google.com/forms>) and a questionnaire was created. The questionnaire included a total of 8 following questions which are as follows:

Question 1: Have you ever had noninvasive facial rejuvenation/contouring/ augmentation using injections of dermal fillers or Botox, done on your face?

Answer: Yes / No

Note: If your answer is “yes”, skip question 2 and 3 and answer question 4 to 8. If your answer is “no”, kindly answer question 2 ,3 and 4)

Question 2:

Would you consider getting treatment of fillers and Botox for enhancing your facial appearance in future?

Answer: Yes / No / May be

Question 3:

If you decide to have facial injection plasty using dermal fillers and Botox, which specialty doctor would you choose?

Answer: (Choose one)

Plastic surgeon / Dermatologist / General Surgeon/ General Physician / Family Physician/ Other

Question 4: In your opinion, overall which healthcare provider is better trained/more skilled/better equipped in performing procedures like injecting dermal fillers and Botox?

Answer: (Choose one)

Plastic surgeon / Dermatologist / General Surgeon / General Physician / Other

Question 5:

Which specialist did you visit for having your procedure of dermal filler/Botox?

Answer: Plastic surgeon/Dermatologist/General Surgeon/General Physician/Family Physician/Other

Question 6:

Are you satisfied with your doctor’s skills and treatment results?

Answer: Yes /No

Question 7: Did you encounter any post treatment complications?

Answer: Yes / No

Question 8: Did your chosen healthcare provider successfully manage your post injection complications? Answer: Yes/No

In addition to the questions listed above, the public also had to provide basic demographic information such as age, gender, occupation and country.

An online link was created as follows <https://forms.gle/h5MTLLHq5f6LrrxH7> and then sent to about 3 to 4000 thousand people.

Sampling of Surveyees: A known scientific technique of “Judgement or purposive sampling” was applied while selection of the potential patients and subjects of this study. Judgement or purposive sampling technique is a type of non- probability sampling (no assurance of every element of whole to become sample) and relies solely on the judgement of the researcher when choosing who to ask to participate. In purposive sampling, patients and the subject of the study are chosen and approached for having certain characteristics. The patients and the subjects of our study were judgmentally or purposely chosen due to having certain attributes such as a keen interest in minimally invasive or noninvasive aesthetic procedures on social media or their display pictures on social media suggesting their possible history with injectable procedures. The researcher is an active user of various highly popular international social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter etc. Since the start of his post graduate training in Plastic surgery, due to his keen interest in cosmetic procedures especially injectables, he has been following a vast number of renowned plastic surgeons, dermatologists, other specialist doctors and nurse practitioners of not only his home country Pakistan but also of many other English-speaking countries such as US, Canada, England, Australia etc. The author followed them for the sake of learning objective and to stay up to date about the advancements of injectable procedures performed all around the world which are also actively advertised using social media plat forms.¹⁵ Additionally being a medical student himself, the author is a member of various online groups and know hundreds of young medical students and doctors, some of which show keen interest in minimally invasive procedures for facial contouring with injectables.

The questionnaire created by the author was converted into an online link:

“<https://forms.gle/h5MTLLHq5f6LrrxH7>” and then purposely sent to hundreds of carefully chosen people from the followers’ list of many renowned dermatologists and plastic surgeons active on Instagram. Judgmentally or purposely, people or potential patients were chosen from the followers’ list of plastic surgeons and dermatologists due to their possible history of having procedures of injectables, based on the assessment of their profile pictures, their interest and following of the particular aesthetic doctor and the researcher’s guess. Moreover, the same questionnaire was randomly sent to people and hundreds of young medical students using simple random sampling method and the responses of the subjects of our study were carefully collected and analyzed.

Results

Response: Out of two to three thousand people who were sent the questionnaire of the survey within a period of 2 weeks, the researcher collected about 201 responses. It is of critical importance that the participants of this online survey were not informed about which specialty does the researcher belong to minimum bias. Below is the summary of results, analyzed by the researcher.

Demographic Characteristics of Survey participants: Gender: Out of 201 participants, 142 are females (70.6%) and 59 are males (29.4%). (Shown in figure 1)

Figure 1

Age: Respondents from the young age of 18 years old to the mature age of 55 all participated in this survey. However, most of the participants, about 70.4% are in their 20s (n=141), 18.4% are in their 30s (n=37), 7.4% are 18 and 19 years old (n=15).1.9% are in their 40s (n=4) and 1.9% are also in their 50s (n=4). (Shown in figure 2)

Figure 2

Occupation: About 36% (n=73) respondents belong to medical profession themselves as mostly undergraduate medical students, general practitioners, Pg. trainees or other specialists. About 21% (n=44) are university students of other majors, and the rest belonged to a vast range of professions such as accountants, bankers, HR managers, models, media personalities, social media influencers, businessmen and women, military personals etc. (Shown in figure 3)

Figure 3

Nearly all of the participants have a college degree and a clear understanding of the nature of noninvasive procedures of facial rejuvenation with fillers and botulinum toxin.

Country: As the information of this section was not mandatory for the participants to fill, some people left this section blank (n=12). However, based on the available data, most of the respondents belonged to the author's home country Pakistan (n=141). Some from other Asian countries such as Thailand (n=12), Philippines (n=11), India (n=8), China (n=2), Saudi Arabia (n=2), Afghanistan (n=2). Few participants from north America and Europe also participated in this survey such as Georgia (n=2), England (n=3), U.S (n=2), Ukraine (n=2) and Russia (n=2). (Shown in figure 4)

Figure 4

Results according to Individual Questions:

1. For the first question, “Have you ever had noninvasive facial rejuvenation/contouring/ augmentation using injections of dermal fillers or Botox, done on your face?”, all 201 participants responded with

160 respondents (79.6%) answered “no” and 41 respondents (20.4%) answered as “yes”. (Shown in figure 5a and 5b)

Question 1: Have you ever had noninvasive facial rejuvenation/contouring/ augmentation using injections of dermal fillers or Botox, done on your face?

Figure 5a

- Total No. of Surveyees: **201**
- No. of participants who answered: **201**
- No. of participants who answered “Yes”: **41 (20.4%)**
- No. of participants who answered “No”: **160 (79.6%)**

Figure 5b

2. For the second question, “Would you consider getting treatment of fillers and Botox for enhancing your facial appearance in future?”, a total of 163 participants responded out of 201, out of 163 respondents 38%(n=62) answered “no”, 33.7%(n=55) answered “maybe” and 28.2% (n= 46) answered as “yes”. (Shown in figure 6a and 6b)

Question 2: Would you consider getting treatment of fillers and Botox for enhancing your facial appearance in future?

Figure 6a

- Total No. of Surveyees: **201**
- No. of participants who answered: **163**
- No. of participants who answered “Yes”: **46 (28.2%)**
- No. of participants who answered “No”: **62 (38%)**
- No. of participants who answered “Maybe”: **55**

Figure 6b

3. For the third question, “If you decide to have facial injection plasty using dermal fillers and Botox, which specialty doctor would you choose?”, multiple choices were given to the participants and they had to choose one option in the given options of ‘Plastic surgeon’, ‘Dermatologist’, ‘General Surgeon’, ‘General Physician’, ‘Family Physician’, ‘nurse practitioner’ and ‘Other’. Out of 201 participants, 160 people responded to this question and 41 chose to leave it blank. Out of 160 people, 95 respondents (59.4%) chose plastic surgeons, 56 people (35%) chose dermatologists, 4 people (2.5%) chose family

physician, 2 people (1.25%) selected general surgeon, 1 person (0.6%) selected nurse practitioner, 1 person (0.6%) couldn't choose any and 1 person (0.6%) chose both the dermatologist and plastic surgeon. (Shown in figure 7a and 7b)

Question 3: If you decide to have facial injection plasty using dermal fillers and Botox, which speciality doctor would you choose?

Figure 7a (According to percentage)

Figure 7b (According to numbers)

- For question 4, “In your opinion, overall which healthcare provider is better trained/more skilled/better equipped in performing procedures like injecting dermal fillers and Botox?”, multiple choices were given to respondents and they had to choose one option. All 201 participants chose to answer this question. According to the results, 122 respondents (60.7%) chose plastic surgeon, 64 respondents

(31.8%) chose dermatologist, 5 respondents (2.4%) chose general surgeon, 2 respondents (0.9%) chose family physician, 5 respondents (2.4%) didn't have any idea about how to answer this question and 1 respondent (0.49%) chose both plastic surgeon and dermatologist. (Shown in figure 8a and 8b)

Figure 8a

- Total number of surveyees: **201**
- Number of participants who answered: **201**
- Number of participants who chose “Plastic Surgeon”: **122**
- Number of participants who chose “Dermatologist”: **64**
- Number of participants who chose “General Surgeon”: **5**
- Number of participants who chose “Family Physician”: **2**
- Number of participants who have no idea: **5**
- Number of participants who chose both “Plastic Surgeon and dermatologist”: **1**

Figure 8b: According to numbers

5. Question No. 5 was aimed towards those 41 patients who have had history of getting facial injectable procedures. The question was, “Which specialist did you visit for having your procedure of dermal filler/Botox?”, to which all 41 of them replied. They had to choose between the options; ‘Plastic surgeon’, ‘Dermatologist’, ‘General Surgeon’, ‘General Physician’, ‘Family Physician’ and ‘Non-medical personal’. Out of 41 patients who answered this question, 22 patients (53.6%) chose plastic surgeons, 17 patients (41.4%) chose dermatologists, 1 patient (2.4%) chose General physician and interestingly 1 (2.4%) of the patients (respondent number 84) wrote non-medical personnel instead of choosing any given option. All 41 patients’ data was carefully analyzed individually and was looked for any significant information related to our research. (Shown in figure 9a and 9b)

Figure 9a (According to percentage)

- Total number of Patients: **41**
- Number of Patients who answered this question: **41**
- Number of Patients who chose “Plastic Surgeon”: **22**
- Number of Patients who chose “Dermatologist”: **17**
- Number of patients who chose “General Surgeon”: **0**
- Number of patients who chose “General Physician”: **1**
- Number of patients who chose “Family Physician”: **0**
- Number of patients who chose “Non-medical personnel”: **1** (Respondent No.84)

Figure 9b: According to numbers

6. For question number 6, “Are you satisfied with your doctor’s skills and treatment results?”. The 41 patients had to choose between ‘yes’ and ‘No’. 31 patients chose the answer ‘yes’ and 10 patients chose the answer ‘no’ (Shown in figure 10a)

Figure 10a: Number of patients' rate of satisfaction from their respective doctors

Out of those 10 patients, who expressed their dissatisfaction with their respective doctors, 5 patients (respondent number 108,130,138,145 and 198) visited dermatologists for filler or toxin treatment, 3 patients (respondent number 143,144 and 200) visited plastic surgeons, 1 patient visited a General Physician (respondent number 72) and one patient (respondent number 184) surprisingly visited non-medical personnel for the sake of facial rejuvenation with fillers and Botox. (Shown in figure 10b and 10c)

Figure 10b: Number of patients showing their level of dissatisfaction with their respective injectors

- Particular patients showing their dissatisfaction from their respective injectors:**
- **Dermatologists:** Respondent number 108,130,138,145 and 198 in survey.
 - **Plastic Surgeons:** Respondent number 143,144 and 200 in survey.
 - **General Physicians:** Respondent number 72 in survey.
 - **Non-medical Personnel:** Respondent number 184 in survey.

Figure 10c

7. For question number 7, “Did you encounter any post treatment complications?”, the 41 patients had to choose again between ‘yes’ and ‘no’. A total of 11 patients out of 41 reported to have post procedure complications, and 30 patients did not report any post procedure complications. (Shown in figure 11a)

Figure 11a

Out of the 11 patients, 5 patients (respondent number 108,130,138,145 and 198) visited dermatologists for treatment, 5 additional patients (respondent number 144,147,183,195 and 200) chose plastic surgeons as their preferred doctors for this treatment and lastly one patient (respondent number 184) reported to have visited non-medical personnel. (Figure 11b)

Figure 11b

Particular patients of each injector reporting posttreatment complications:

- **Dermatologists:** Respondent number **108,130,138,145 and 198** in survey.
- **Plastic Surgeons:** Respondent number **144,147,183,195 and 200** in survey.
- **Non-medical personnel:** Respondent number **184** in survey.

Figure 11c

The point which is to be noted is that in case of dermatologists, according to the data, the patients who showed

their dissatisfaction from dermatologist injectors also happen to be the same who reported to have experienced post treatment complications. These are the same 5 patients (respondent number 108,130,138,145 and 198) as clearly shown in figure 10c and 11c. However, in the case of plastic surgeons' patients, initially only 3 patients (respondent number 143,144 and 200 in survey) showed their dissatisfaction from their plastic surgeon injectors as suggested by the data in figure 10c. Later on, out of the above 3 patients, 2 patients (respondent number 144 and 200) also reported to have experienced post injection complications. Additionally, 3 more patients (respondent number 147,183 and 195) of plastic surgeons reported to have experienced post treatment complications (figure 11b and 11c). But interestingly these 3 patients didn't show their dissatisfaction with their plastic surgeon injectors as suggested by the data of question 6 (figure 10a,10b and 10c). Lastly, the patient who chose nonmedical personnel as his/her injector showed not only dissatisfaction from her injector as suggested by the data of question 6 (figure 10b and 10c), but also reported to have faced post procedure complications.

8. The last question (question number 8) was, "Did your chosen healthcare provider successfully manage your posttreatment complications?", to which the respondents had to answer by choosing between 'yes' and 'no'. According to the results out of 11 patients who reported to have faced post procedure complications in the previous question (figure 11a,11b and 11c), 4 patients (respondent number 108,145, 184 and 198) chose "No" and the other 7 patients chose the answer 'yes'. (Shown in figure 12a and 12b)

Figure 12a

- Particular patients whose chosen injectors couldn't successfully manage their post treatment complications:
1. Respondent no. **108**
 2. Respondent no. **145**
 3. Respondent no. **184**
 4. Respondent no. **198**

Figure 12b

Out of the 7 patients who showed their satisfaction with their chosen healthcare provider in terms of successfully treating their post treatment complications, 5 patients (number:144,147,183,195 and 200) were treated by plastic surgeons and 2 patients (number 130 and 138) were treated by dermatologists. (Figure 12c and 12d)

Figure 12c

Particular patients whose chosen injectors successfully manage their post treatment complications:

Patients of Plastic Surgeons

- Respondent no. **144**
- Respondent no. **147**
- Respondent no. **183**
- Respondent no. **195**
- Respondent no. **200**

Patients of Dermatologists

- Respondent no. **130**
- Respondent no. **138**

Figure 12d

However, 3 of the patients of dermatologists (respondent number:108,145 and 198), who initially reported to encounter post treatment complications in question 7 (figure 11a,11b and 11c), also reported that their respective doctors didn't successfully treat their post-operative complications by choosing "No" as the answer to question 8. Additionally, one patient (respondent number 184) also chose the answer "No" for question number 8. (Figure 12e and 12f)

Figure 12e

Particular patients of dermatologists with unsuccessful management of postop complications:

- Respondent no.**108**
- Respondent no. **145**
- Respondent no. **198**

Additional patient, with unsuccessful management of postop complications:

- Respondent no.**184**

Figure 12f

By carefully analyzing the data of this particular patient, it was discovered that this patient was a middle aged

housewife who had her injection rejuvenation done by a non-medical personnel, as reported earlier by her in the results of question 6, she showed dissatisfaction with her injector then in question 7's answer she reported to have faced post procedure complications and in the answer of question 8, it was clear that her injector couldn't treat her complications successfully which may be is the reason of her dissatisfaction with her injector.

Therefore, it can be inferred that higher dissatisfaction of patients with their respective injectors is directly proportional to the inability of their injectors to successfully treat their post procedure complications. At the same time, even if post treatment complications are incurred, the successful management and treatment of such complications lead to a higher degree of patients' satisfaction with their respective injectors.

Conclusion

The subjects chosen for the conduction of this study belong to the educated class of the society. Most of the study subjects themselves are medical students and doctors which gives them a higher degree of credibility in terms of understanding the injectable products, which doctor or professional to choose as injectors and possible adverse events related to facial injections. Regardless of the country and region, females are always more interested in facial rejuvenation with dermal fillers and botulinum neurotoxin. People in their 20s, among all age groups, show the keenest interest in enhancing their facial esthetics with nonsurgical methodology, especially with fillers and neuromodulators. The people who have had facial rejuvenation procedures are still in minority but there is a vast majority who do consider getting their faces contoured via injection plasty in future. There is a lot of future prospect for plastic surgeons in noninvasive facial plasty with filler and toxins as they are precepted by the general public as the most trained, best equipped and highly trained professionals in fulfilling the public's need. In short, when it comes to facial injection plasty, plastic surgeons are trusted and preferred over all other medical specialists by the general public as far as our data is concerned.

Moreover, patients who have already had nonsurgical facial plasty at plastic surgeon's clinic show a higher degree of satisfaction with results and safety profile of these procedures as compared to other doctors. Patients always show a higher degree of satisfaction and happiness with their injectors, if they experience minimum complications. However, if post procedure complications do occur and are inevitable, their successful management by the doctor actually keeps the patient satisfied and he develops a trust on his doctor. Our data suggests that plastic surgeon' patients of nonsurgical injection plasty report of greater degree of satisfaction with minimum adverse effects with their doctors. However, the margin of error is always there, as there are so many factors involved other than the skill of the doctor such as preoperative care, product type, hypersensitivity in patients, operation room settings, comorbidities in patients, post-operative care etc.

Our research may not prove anything as which specialist is better. We do not intend to create any controversy as both the plastic surgeons and dermatologists are highly trained professionals, preferred by the public for getting their medical aesthetic treatments. With increasing presence of nonmedical professionals in the society performing injectable procedures, causing complications as they lack the basic training and knowledge in this field, it is imperative for plastic surgeons and other aesthetic doctors such as dermatologists to immediately take strong steps to create a higher degree of awareness in general public and warning them of the potential risks

involved.

References

- 1 Friedman PM, Jih MH, Burns AJ, Geronemus RG, Kimyai-Asadi A, Goldberg LH. Nonphysician practice of dermatologic surgery: the Texas perspective. *Dermatol Surg*. 2004 Jun;30(6):857-63. doi: 10.1111/j.1524-4725.2004.30253.x. PMID: 15171762.
- 2 Resneck JS Jr, Kimball AB. Who else is providing care in dermatology practices? Trends in the use of nonphysician clinicians. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2008 Feb;58(2):211-6. doi: 10.1016/j.jaad.2007.09.032. PMID: 18222319.
- 3 Mobayed N, Nguyen JK, Jagdeo J. Minimally Invasive Facial Cosmetic Procedures for the Millennial Aesthetic Patient. *J Drugs Dermatol*. 2020 Jan 1;19(1):100-103. doi: 10.36849/JDD.2020.4641. PMID: 32395973.
- 4 Sheen D, Clarkson E. Botox and Dermal Fillers: Review and Its Role in the Dental Office. *Dent Clin North Am*. 2020 Apr;64(2):325-339. doi: 10.1016/j.cden.2019.12.002. Epub 2020 Jan 17. PMID: 32111272.
- 5 Kosiński J, Jarecki J, Przepiorcka-Kosińska J, Ratajczak M. HYALURONIC ACID IN ORTHOPEDICS. *Wiad Lek*. 2020;73(9 cz. 1):1878-1881. PMID: 33099534.
- 6 Hotta T. Core curriculum for plastic surgical nursing: dermal fillers. *Plast Surg Nurs*. 2008 Jul-Sep;28(3):131-5. doi: 10.1097/01.PSN.0000335813.92411.02. PMID: 18794737.
- 7 Jolly R, Bhalla M, Zakir R, Joshi N. Visual loss from dermal fillers. *Eur J Ophthalmol*. 2019 Jun 12:1120672119855856. doi: 10.1177/1120672119855856. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 31187644.
- 8 Rauso R, Nicoletti GF, Zerbinati N, Lo Giudice G, Fragola R, Tartaro G. Complications Following Self-Administration of Hyaluronic Acid Fillers: Literature Review. *Clin Cosmet Investig Dermatol*. 2020 Oct 14;13:767-771. doi: 10.2147/CCID.S276959. PMID: 33116740; PMCID: PMC7569170.
- 9 Kassir M, Gupta M, Galadari H, Kroumpouzou G, Katsambas A, Lotti T, Vojvodic A, Grabbe S, Juchems E, Goldust M. Complications of botulinum toxin and fillers: A narrative review. *J Cosmet Dermatol*. 2020 Mar;19(3):570-573. doi: 10.1111/jocd.13266. Epub 2019 Dec 30. PMID: 31889407.
- 10 Sorensen EP, Urman C. Cosmetic complications: rare and serious events following botulinum toxin and soft tissue filler administration. *J Drugs Dermatol*. 2015 May;14(5):486-91. PMID: 25942667.
- 11 Jolly R, Bhalla M, Zakir R, Joshi N. Visual loss from dermal fillers. *Eur J Ophthalmol*. 2019 Jun 12:1120672119855856. doi: 10.1177/1120672119855856. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 31187644.
- 12 Adamson AS, Suarez EA, McDaniel P, Leiphart PA, Zeitany A, Kirby JS. Geographic Distribution of Nonphysician Clinicians Who Independently Billed Medicare for Common Dermatologic Services in 2014. *JAMA Dermatol*. 2018 Jan 1;154(1):30-36. doi: 10.1001/jamadermatol.2017.5039. PMID: 29167867; PMCID: PMC5833583.
- 13 Bangash, Haider K. MD*; Ibrahim, Omar A. MD, PhD†,‡; Green, Lawrence J. MD§; Alam, Murad MD, MSCII; Eisen, Daniel B. MD¶; Armstrong, April W. MD, MPH¶¶ Who Do You Prefer? A Study of Public

Preferences for Health Care Provider Type in Performing Cutaneous Surgery and Cosmetic Procedures in the United States, *Dermatologic Surgery*: June 2014 - Volume 40 - Issue 6 - p 671-678

doi: 10.1111/dsu.0000000000000016

14 D'Amico, Richard A. M.D.; Saltz, Renato M.D.; Rohrich, Rod J. M.D.; Kinney, Brian M.D.; Haeck, Phillip M.D.; Gold, Alan H. M.D.; Singer, Robert M.D.; Jewell, Mark L. M.D., P.C.; Eaves, Felmont III M.D. Risks and Opportunities for Plastic Surgeons in a Widening Cosmetic Medicine Market: Future Demand, Consumer Preferences, and Trends in Practitioners' Services, *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*: May 2008 - Volume 121 - Issue 5 - p 1787-1792

doi: 10.1097/PRS.0b013e31816c3c49

15 Cho MJ, Furnas HJ, Rohrich RJ. A Primer on Social Media Use by Young Plastic Surgeons. *Plast Reconstr Surg*. 2019 May;143(5):1533-1539. doi: 10.1097/PRS.0000000000005533. PMID: 31033838

Corresponding Author: Professor Dr. Li Guang Shuai M.D, PhD, aged 45, is the Head of Department of Plastic Surgery, First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Henan, China. Dr. Li is native to China.

Co-Author 1: Dr. Muhammad Tipu Sultan M.D, aged 28, is doing his postgraduate residency in Plastic Surgery under the supervision of the 'corresponding author' at First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Henan, China. Dr. Sultan is of Pakistani origin.

Co-Author 2: Dr. Liu Wen Hui M.D, PhD, aged 35, is a senior surgeon at Department of Plastic Surgery, First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Henan, China. Dr. Liu is native to China.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

